

Rheological Studies of Bentonite Suspension during Interaction with Alkali Salts of Higher Fatty Acids

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Flow properties of bentonite suspension during interaction with some alkali salts of higher fatty acids and the stabilising action of the same in presence of some strong electrolytes were studied. The rheological parameters were correlated with the different modes of particle interaction in the suspension.

The flow properties of a ceramic slip containing bentonite can be very easily adjusted with the help of suitable additives. The effects of several electrolytes on the stability of bentonite suspension have been studied by various workers¹.

In the present work, the flow properties of bentonite suspension during interaction with some alkali salts of higher fatty acids have been studied. Further, the effect on rheological properties of the addition of some strong electrolytes to this bentonite suspension in presence of some large ions generated from the alkali salts of higher fatty acids have been also examined. From such studies the different rheological parameter, e.g. yield value and plastic viscosity are calculated and the results correlated with the different modes of particle association in solution.

Results and Discussion

From chemical analysis and other characteristics of the sample the true montmorillonitic nature of the bentonite was evident : SiO₂, 51.30; Al₂O₃, 27.31; Fe₂O₃, 1.41; MgO, 1.36%; L.O.I., 14.89%; C.E.C., 97.21 meq./100g; DTA peak temp., 155, 565 (endo), 940 (exo); yield value, 68.24×10^{-3} dyne cm⁻¹ (of 10% bentonite suspension); plastic viscosity, 16.2342×10^3 poise (of 10% bentonite suspension).

The results of interaction of three salts of

TABLE 1—RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF 10% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION

Suspension	Volume of 0.1% solution added ml	Yield value $\times 10^{-3}$ dyne cm ⁻²	Plastic viscosity $\times 10^{-3}$ poise
In presence of Na-oleate	10	63.935	15.18
	20	93.83	16.11
	60	423.088	9.44
	80	8.53	17.737
In presence of Na-palmitate	10	366.79	4.510
	20	399.204	12.206
	30	511.80	12.005
	40	385.556	11.965
In presence of Na-laurate	10	162.07	15.753
	20	187.66	14.851
	30	429.912	12.626
	40	20.472	15.212

higher fatty acids with an aqueous suspension of bentonite (Table 1) reveal that the non-Newtonian nature was retained in each case although the magnitude of yield values was different depending on the nature of interaction. In most of the cases the yield values were higher compared to that obtained without any additive on progressive addition of the salts of fatty acids. Yield values gradually increased upto an addition of a certain volume (60 ml) and then decreased sharply. This was the relation with all the alkali salts of fatty acids. At the initial point of addition the sequence of the alkali salts of fatty acids with respect to the yield value was palmitate > laurate > oleate.

This was also maintained at the final point of addition where the yield value reduced to such an extent that it was lower than that of pure bentonite suspension. The reduction in viscosity might be due to the lowering of particle forces due to the separation of the double layers in presence of the ions of the alkali salts of the higher fatty acids. Minimum viscosity was achieved with palmitate and maximum with oleate. The sequence of the addition with respect to plastic viscosity might be presented in the following way at the initial stage of addition : laurate > oleate > palmitate, and at the final stage, oleate > laurate > palmitate.

From the relationship it was evident that plastic viscosity and yield value were not always inter-related properties. The mobile ions generated from the alkali salts of the higher fatty acids had particularly no influence on the mode of particle interaction as both the exchanging and the exchangeable cations were the same, i.e. sodium.

From a study of the mixed interaction, i.e. interaction of the clay suspension with both the alkali salts of higher fatty acids and strong electrolyte (Tables 2 and 3), it was observed that during interaction with calcium chloride, all the higher fatty acid salts showed non-Newtonian characteristics as indicated by the existence of the yield value. At the initial point of addition of the alkali salts of higher fatty acids in presence of CaCl_2 , two inflexion points were noticed in the yield value curves. The yield values were always lower than the original one. This might be due to either greater stabilisation of the suspension or complete elimination of solvent-solute interaction.

TABLE 2—RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF 10% NA-BENTONITE SUSPENSION IN PRESENCE OF ELECTROLYTE

Electrolyte	Yield value $\times 10^{-3}$ dyne cm^{-2}	Plastic viscosity $\times 10^{-3}$ poise
CaCl_2	344.61	10.819
$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	37.53	20.623

TABLE 3—RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF 10% NA-BENTONITE SUSPENSIONS DURING MIXED INTERACTIONS

	Volume of 0.1% solution added ml	Yield value $\times 10^{-3}$ dyne cm^{-2}	Plastic viscosity $\times 10^{-3}$ poise
With CaCl_2 + Na-oleate	10	597.10	14.550
	20	25.59	20.142
	40	349.73	16.354
	60	400.91	16.053
	80	192.79	20.443
With CaCl_2 + Na-laurate	10	59.71	18.038
	20	284.90	15.512
	40	90.41	16.955
	60	11.94	18.819
	80	0	14.914
With CaCl_2 + Na-palmitate	10	433.32	16.414
	20	315.61	17.357
	40	578.33	14.610
	60	499.85	15.933
	80	351.43	20.803
With $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ + Na-oleate	10	0	15.513
	20	0	14.01
	40	170.60	21.646
	60	0	24.652
	80	460.60	15.633
With $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ + Na-palmitate	10	119.42	24.050
	20	46.06	29.930
	40	469.15	20.142
	60	696.04	17.557
	80	767.70	18.218
With $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ + Na-laurate	10	0	19.120
	20	0	19.120
	40	153.54	20.443
	60	435.03	15.935
	80	417.97	19.241

In case of palmitate, viscosity initially decreased showing a maximum at 20 ml addition, then decreased but another inflexion was noticed at 40 ml. Although oleate showed same relationship but in case of laurate, the nature of the curve was just the reverse. This was due to different modes of particle association.

The results of the mixed interaction with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ as electrolyte shows some differences specially with respect to the change of yield value. The increase of yield value was higher compared to that obtained with CaCl_2 solution. Complete disappearance of yield value was observed upto 20 ml addition with oleate and laurate. Maximum yield value was achieved with

palmitate solution. Thus the behaviour of the salts of the fatty acids appeared to be very much selective.

The plastic viscosity during mixed interaction with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ was maximum with sodium palmitate. Thus from the increase of yield values during mixed interaction in presence of electrolytes like CaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, it appeared that within the range of organic additives the agglomeration of particles could be prevented.

From a study of the sedimentation (Tables 4-6) it was observed that alkali metal salts of the fatty acids showed more or less dispersive nature as was the case with simple bentonite suspension. Maximum swelling was observed with Na-oleate and minimum with laurate.

TABLE 4—SWELLING VOLUME* OF 5% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION DURING INTERACTION WITH OR WITHOUT ELECTROLYTE

Electrolyte added	Swelling volume (ml)
Nil	Turbid, complete dispersion
CaCl_2	17.5
$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	17.0

* Swelling volume has been defined as the volume of the clay sedimented at equilibrium in presence of the interacted liquid and it was studied at 5% clay concentration with 0.75 meq electrolyte (CaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$) per 100 ml of the suspension.

Complete sedimentation with separation of clear supernatant liquor was observed with CaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution which was due to the compression of the diffused double layer, leading to flocculation. When this suspension was interacted with increasing amount of sodium salts of fatty acids no significant change of sediment volume was observed. On the other hand, the sediment volume decreased to some extent in some cases. Thus the alkali metal salts of the higher fatty acids were not sufficient enough to overcome the flocculating action of the electrolytes.

TABLE 5—SWELLING VOLUME OF 5% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION DURING INTERACTION WITH Na-SALTS OF FATTY ACIDS

Na-salts used	Volume of 0.1% solution added (ml)	Swelling volume (ml)
Na-oleate	10	98
	20	98
	40	96
	60	98
	80	95
Na-palmitate	10	95
	20	95
	40	96
	60	96
	80	96
Na-laurate	10	97
	20	95
	40	96
	60	97
	80	96

TABLE 6—SWELLING VOLUME OF 5% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION DURING MIXED INTERACTION

Sodium salt of fatty acid + electrolyte	Volume of 0.1% solution added (ml)	Swelling volume (ml)
Na-oleate + CaCl_2	10	12.50
	20	14.00
	40	15.25
	60	14.50
	80	14.50
Na-laurate + CaCl_2	10	15.50
	20	16.00
	40	15.50
	60	16.00
	80	16.00
Na-palmitate + CaCl_2	10	16.00
	20	16.00
	40	18.00
	60	15.50
	80	16.00
Na-oleate + $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	10	13.00
	20	13.00
	40	14.00
	60	13.00
	80	13.00
Na-palmitate + $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	10	14.00
	20	12.50
	40	14.50
	60	13.50
	80	16.50
Na-laurate + $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	10	12.00
	20	11.50
	40	14.00
	60	13.50
	80	15.00

Conclusions : (i) The interaction of clay suspension with the sodium salts of higher fatty acids was anionic type and the system became complicated by the presence of high molecular organic compounds. (ii) The lowering of plastic viscosity of the clay suspension in presence of sodium salts of the higher molecular fatty acids might be due to the reduction of the particle forces produced by the separation of double layer in presence of large ion. (iii) In the case of mixed interaction, the behaviour of the salts of higher fatty acids appeared to be very much selective. The electrolyte itself had a strong tendency to react with the ions generated from the salts of higher fatty acids.

Experimental

Tinpahari bentonite was selected for the present investigation. The clay was purified from its associated impurities and converted to monoionic sodium form. It was characterised by chemical analysis, cation-exchange capacity measurement and thermal analysis. The flow properties were studied in a McMichael bob and cup viscometer.

A 10% bentonite suspension was selected for the present study and all the interactions were carried out at this concentration. In the first phase of work, interaction of the clay suspension with sodium salts of the three fatty acids, namely, oleic, palmitic and lauric (each at a concentration

of 0.1%) was carried out. The suspensions were equilibrated at room temperature for a period of 16 h followed by shaking in a mechanical shaker for 2 h.

To study mixed interaction, CaCl_2 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ were selected. Fixed amount of these electrolytes, i.e. 1.5 meq was used and the proportion of 0.1% solution of alkali salts of fatty acids was gradually increased. The rheological study was performed under similar condition as discussed earlier. Flow curves were drawn in each case from which the rheological parameters, such as yield values and plastic viscosities were calculated.

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